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**TOLERANCE AND ECOLOGY OF CULTURE IN THE ISLAMIC
TRADITION**

Abstract: Environmental ethics is becoming an increasingly important factor in contemporary environmental discourse, attracting widespread interest from religious studies and environmental humanities. The Quran is widely recognised as a source rich in deep ethical and cosmological meanings that challenge anthropocentrism and lay the foundation for a respectful attitude towards the natural world. A special feature of the Quranic worldview is the recognition of all beings, both animate and inanimate, as spiritually conscious and actively participating in the divine creation. This theocentric vision challenges the hierarchical and anthropocentric interpretations that dominate contemporary Central Asia. Over the past two decades, scholars such as Sarah Tlili and Anna M. Gade have made great efforts to bring to the fore a deep ecological understanding of the Quran. Their writings emphasise the need to reassess the concept of human viceroyalty (caliph) in light of climate change and environmental degradation. However, despite a growing body of research, few studies have addressed the question of how Islamic metaphysics, particularly concepts such as tawhid (unity) and amanah (trust), can be applied in environmental ethics. This article attempts to fill this gap by combining hermeneutic analysis and ethnographic data from Central Asia to illustrate how the Quran inspires spiritually integrated ecology. The study demonstrates how justice and mercy are manifested as ethical imperatives for caring for the environment, and how understanding humanity as God's creation leads to a more sustainable interaction between humans and the natural world. In doing so, this article contributes to a theocentric paradigm that both challenges and enriches

contemporary ecological discourse, which is rooted in Western secularism. The Islamic perspective on environmental ethics is grounded in environmental pluralism and inclusivity.

Keywords: environmental ethics of the Quran, ecology, theocentrism, anthropocentrism, amana (trust), and tawhid (unity)

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that religious texts often encode moral messages through indirect forms such as symbolism and rhetorical emphasis. This is especially true in the Quran, where natural elements are frequently invoked not simply as background but as active participants in a cosmic moral order. This paper examines how divine oaths, for instance, elevate non-human phenomena—ranging from figs and olives to stars and animals—by swearing upon them. Such gestures, as noted by early exegetes like Qatadah, reflect divine esteem and thereby disrupt anthropocentric hierarchies.

Although few studies have addressed the problem of how Quranic rhetoric reshapes the human-nature relationship, this paper proposes that these motifs invite a reimagining of kinship beyond species. It has now been suggested that the Quran de-centres humanity not as an act of devaluation, but as a means of integrating humans into a broader network of devotion and submission to God. In this way, the non-human world is not merely a resource for human use but serves as a theological, moral, and ontological interlocutor. This paper aims to highlight how the Quran promotes an ethic of humility, attentiveness, and reverence toward creation by foregrounding its signs, its inner consciousness, and its participation in divine praise. In so doing, the paper contributes to a growing body of literature that situates Islamic thought within contemporary environmental ethics. The following sections will examine each of the three motifs in turn, providing a close textual reading alongside insights from Hadith literature and contemporary Islamic ecological philosophy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopts a qualitative, hermeneutical approach grounded in the close reading of selected Quranic passages and supported by classical and contemporary exegetical literature. The aim is to identify and interpret ecological motifs embedded in the Quranic worldview and analyse their ethical and theological implications. The methodology is interdisciplinary, drawing on Islamic theology, Quranic studies, and environmental humanities. It relies on the interpretive tools of tafsir (Quranic exegesis), supplemented by Hadith literature, to contextualise prophetic teachings on the natural world. This is complemented by contemporary ethnographic observations from Muslim-majority contexts (particularly Central Asia), which illuminate how ecological ethics grounded in Quranic motifs are embodied in everyday religious practice.

Through this blended approach, the study situates Quranic environmental ethics not only as a textual phenomenon but also as a lived tradition shaped by affect, ritual, and community. This method also challenges Eurocentric and colonial

epistemologies that dominate environmental ethics by foregrounding Islamic cosmologies and moral grammars. [Agushi, M., & Ali, M. A. 2024. p 949].

In doing so, the paper follows the model of “ethics-as-practice” used in environmental anthropology, where meaning is generated not only through formal doctrines but through emotional, embodied, and relational interactions with the environment. Fieldwork insights and secondary ethnographies serve to validate how Quranic themes, such as divine oaths, non-human agency, and the spiritual sensitivity of creation, continue to shape ethical attitudes toward the more-than-human world.

Islamic environmental ethics is a rapidly expanding field within both religious studies and environmental humanities. Recent scholarship has challenged the assumption that the Quran offers little to environmental discourse. While the Quran does not contain systematic ecological legislation, it provides an ethical and cosmological framework that deconstructs anthropocentrism and promotes reverence for the non-human world.

Scholars such as Sarra Tlili, Anna M. Gade, and Ibrahim Ozdemir argue that ethnocentrism, rather than anthropocentrism, underpins the Quranic vision of creation. Tlili, S. in particular, emphasises the Quran’s attribution of spiritual agency and consciousness to non-human beings. In this view, animals, stones, and celestial bodies are not merely passive resources but spiritual participants in the divine order. [Tlili, 2012.p 23].

Dr. Tlili presents a theological argument that both patriarchy and anthropocentrism contradict tawhid, the oneness of God. By centring anything other than God—be it man, species, or gender—these ideologies constitute shirk. In this worldview, decentering the human is a moral reorientation, and humans are but one among many creatures striving to please God. [Tlili, S. 2020].

Hierarchical readings of the human–nature relationship are also problematized in Tlili’s work, where nature is described as spiritually aware and capable of praise, choice, and will. Even classical exegetes like Fakhr al-Din al-Razi acknowledged the theological complexity of verses addressing non-human creation. [Tlili, S. 2012. p 45]

Gade A. argues that in secular environmental humanities, anthropocentrism is often assumed to be the primary ethical problem. However, she critiques this framing as rooted in post-Enlightenment Christian traditions, whereas Islamic cosmology offers an alternate theocentric moral grammar. [Gade, A. M. 2019.].

Both scholars emphasise that decentering humans restores moral balance rather than devaluing humanity. The Quran affirms the sanctity of all creation and condemns any form of idolatry that displaces God from the centre, including speciesism and patriarchy. These perspectives significantly contribute to Islamic ecological thought, particularly in global contexts such as Central Asia, where environmental preaching integrates themes of justice, mercy, and the eschatological consequences of human actions. Exegetical engagement with concepts such as amanah (trust) and khalifa (vicegerency) has been revitalised by scholars and

activists seeking to redefine stewardship as responsibility rather than domination [Ozdemir, I. 2008. p. 151].

Islamic ethics, rooted in theocentrism, offer a vision of interdependence and accountability that has the potential to enrich global environmental thought, not just for Muslims, but for humanity as a whole. [Hashmi, F. 2023. p 45–61.].

Islam, she argued, offers an alternative cosmology and moral language. From a Quranic perspective, environmental catastrophe is not simply a result of human action in a materialist vacuum, but of moral failure within a divinely authored context. Human actions carry ethical weight because they are situated within God’s creation and judged by divine standards [Ozdemir, I. 1997. Ozdemir, I. 2022. p 90.].

Islamic teachings, therefore, can contribute a profound moral and spiritual dimension to public discussions—one capable of grappling with existential crises such as climate change, extinction, and ecological collapse. Even in secular discourse, this spiritual grammar helps articulate what Gade called “the unthinkable”—the unbearable weight of environmental loss. [Gade, A. M. 2019.].

A recurring theme in the literature is the Quranic portrayal of the natural world as both obedient and knowing. Passages that describe mountains fearing God, skies reacting to blasphemy, or the earth responding to divine commands suggest a distributed moral agency across creation. Exegetes like al-Razi recognised the mystery and theological weight of such depictions, even when they could not be rationally explained. [Khalid, F. 2019.].

Moreover, Islamic ecological thought increasingly engages with contemporary environmental challenges through legal and philosophical extensions of traditional categories. Concepts such as al-amana (the Trust) and khalifa (vicegerency) have been reinterpreted in modern Islamic environmentalism to stress accountability and custodianship. However, critiques persist regarding their anthropocentric misreadings in colonial and post-colonial periods.

In parallel, the field of environmental humanities—especially as practised in Western academia—often emphasises affective ethics (e.g., wonder, care, humility) as foundational to ecological responsibility. While these sentiments are sometimes rooted in post-Protestant Romanticism, they resonate with Islamic teachings that urge emulation of non-human devotion and invite humans to ponder the signs (ayat) of God in nature. [Mukhtar, M., & Todd, M.-J. 2023. p 23-00517].

This paper contributes to this growing body of research by closely examining Quranic motifs that construct a spiritually alive universe and promote ecological humility. In doing so, it aligns with scholars who argue that the Quran fosters kinship with the non-human world, not by asserting equality of being, but through shared devotion and common participation in divine praise.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The findings from this study illuminate a growing movement within Islamic environmental thought that reorients ethics away from anthropocentric models and toward a theocentric, relational, and spiritually integrated framework. Three core themes emerged from textual analysis and ethnographic observation:

Integration of the Seen and the Unseen

Islamic ecological ethics emphasises an epistemological model that includes both empirical observation and metaphysical awareness. Echoing classical Sufi cosmologies, contemporary Muslim thinkers and communities recognise the ontological significance of unseen realities—such as divine will, cosmic harmony, and eschatological accountability—within ecological contexts. The Quranic portrayal of nature as sentient and spiritually active reinforces this dual vision.

Dr. Sarah Tlili (2012), addressed the nuanced question of human exceptionalism in the Quran by focusing on the concept of *amanah* (trust). While the Quran often critiques human beings, it also singles them out as the bearers of this unique trust, one that even the heavens, the earth, and the mountains declined to accept [Quran 33:72]. This choice suggests a particular kind of responsibility rather than superiority.

Muslim exegetes have long interpreted this to mean that only humans are ultimately eligible for Paradise, even though non-human creatures may also be judged in the afterlife. However, the Quran does not exhaustively describe the fate of all beings, indicating that its guidance is deliberately human-focused, not because humans are central to creation, but because they require moral direction.

Dr. Tlili revisited traditional assumptions about free will, noting that while many scholars assert that only humans, angels, and jinn possess rational agency, a closer reading of the Quran—and observable behaviour in the natural world—challenges this. Animals, for instance, display significant volition, and the Quran frequently addresses inanimate beings as if they possess consciousness and responsiveness [e.g., Quran 41:11]. Dr. Tlili concluded that assuming a strict binary between human free will and natural determinism is both theologically unfounded and ecologically harmful.

Ethics of Mercy and Justice in Environmental Praxis

The study documented widespread references in Central Asian Islamic discourse to divine justice and mercy as both theological imperatives and environmental strategies. From sermons to grassroots movements, ecological responsibility is framed not only as a stewardship role but as a condition for attaining divine mercy. This relational ethic expands the traditional Islamic binary of vertical (God–human) and horizontal (human–human) ethics to include a third axis: the environmental.

Building on this, she warned that modern readings of the Quran—especially those shaped by the pressures of colonialism and modernisation—have become increasingly anthropocentric. This shift, she argued, is not without consequence. Just as patriarchy has harmed women, so too has anthropocentrism led to ecological degradation. She cited influential modernist *tafsir* (exegesis) that interprets humanity's role as *khalifa* (vicegerent) to mean dominance over nature—an interpretation she critiqued as "very destructive." Dr. Tlili called for a critical reassessment of inherited interpretations, encouraging Muslims to reread the Quran with fresh eyes and ecological urgency. Rather than seeing nature as inert or utilitarian, we must recognise its spiritual agency and God-given integrity. This is

not only theologically sound but crucial for addressing the environmental crises we face.

A central result of this inquiry is the challenge posed to hierarchical readings of creation. Quranic depictions of non-human beings as willful, obedient, and spiritually attuned undermine assumptions of human superiority. The notion of *sakhkhar* (subjugation) is reinterpreted not as domination but as an act of divine mercy, inviting a humbler human stance within a mutual web of interdependence. Textual and ethnographic data support the idea that agency, consciousness, and moral worth are distributed across creation.

This article has explored how Islamic environmental ethics, particularly as articulated in the Quran and interpreted through classical and contemporary lenses, constitute a rich, multi-dimensional ethical framework. Far from offering only general or symbolic guidance, the Quran provides an integrated ecological worldview grounded in spiritual ontology, relational responsibility, and epistemological humility. By examining three key Quranic motifs—divine oaths, the inner state of creation, and creation as a sign—the research highlights how the Quran repositions the human not as a central agent of control, but as a moral actor among many beings within a theocentric cosmos.

A foundational element of this ethical reorientation is the Quran's persistent disruption of anthropocentrism. Divine oaths by non-human beings, depictions of animals and stones as spiritually aware, and portrayals of cosmic sorrow at blasphemy all suggest that creation is not inert or mechanistic, but alive with devotion and agency. In this framework, nature is not merely a backdrop for human moral development but an active witness, participant, and even teacher in the divine order. This challenges dominant Euro-American ecological models that often dichotomise the material and the spiritual, or relegate nature to a passive resource.

The Quran's emphasis on the emotional and devotional states of non-human beings – trees, stones, stars, and animals – suggests that reverence, awe, and a sense of kinship with the non-human world are foundational to Islamic ethics. Such spiritual and emotional attitudes are increasingly recognised by scholars across traditions as necessary conditions for effective environmental stewardship. By fostering this affective dimension, the Quran lays the groundwork for an ethics of care, wonder, and humility that stands in contrast to extractive and technocratic approaches to nature.

Moreover, the Quranic articulation of *amanah* (trust) offers a compelling paradigm of human responsibility that avoids the pitfalls of both nihilistic guilt and anthropocentric triumphalism. The acceptance of this trust by humankind, which the heavens, earth, and mountains declined, is not presented as evidence of superiority but as a sober assignment—one that invites critique and reflection. As Dr. Sarah Tlili and other scholars have emphasised, this trust is not an elevation of status but a call to moral accountability. The consequences of failing to uphold this trust, as evident in the ecological degradation and climate injustice we witness today, serve as a warning and a summons to reimagine human agency.

Ethnographic research in Muslim-majority contexts such as Central Asia provides empirical support for these Quranic principles. Preaching and community practices grounded in themes of mercy, justice, and intergenerational responsibility show how Islamic ecological ethics function as living traditions. Acts of compassion toward animals, water-sharing obligations, and weekly rituals tied to cosmic awareness (such as Friday's special significance) demonstrate the continuity of Quranic cosmology with ethical praxis. These practices are not modern inventions or adaptations, but rather natural extensions of long-standing Islamic teachings, now reactivated with ecological urgency. [Setia, A. 2010. p 23–46.].

In tandem, legal traditions within Islam—particularly those concerning water rights—demonstrate how jurisprudential reasoning complements ethical commitments. The concept of the “right to thirst” in Islamic law, which applies to both humans and animals, exemplifies a shared moral economy rooted in divine justice. The understanding that water, a central Quranic symbol and resource, is to be accessed equitably and never wholly owned underscores Islam's alignment with environmental justice principles. It also reveals how Islamic law can enrich contemporary discussions on the commons, stewardship, and sustainable governance. [Yusuf, M., & Marjuni, K. N. 2022. p 246–263.].

At the same time, both scholars and practitioners caution against oversimplified applications of Islamic ethics. Extractive interpretations, such as reading the Quran's concept of khalifa (vicegerency) as divine license to dominate nature, have already caused theological and ecological harm. These interpretations, often shaped by colonial paradigms and modernist apologetics, require reevaluation. The Quran, when read attentively, subverts such notions and calls instead for mutual dependency, spiritual humility, and reverence for all creation.

Finally, the Islamic emphasis on tawḥīd—the absolute oneness of God—offers a powerful ontological critique of all forms of domination, including patriarchy, speciesism, and nationalism. As Dr. Tlili argued, placing humans at the centre of creation is a form of shirk (associating partners with God), thereby disrupting the divine balance of the cosmos. In this light, de-centring the human is not a demotion but a restoration of spiritual clarity and ethical coherence.

Thus, the Quran does not simply call for “protecting nature” in the modern sense. It demands a spiritual recalibration of our worldview—one that recognises the moral agency of non-human beings, the interwoven nature of justice and mercy, and the sacredness of all life. By integrating theology, practice, jurisprudence, and eschatology, Islamic environmental ethics contribute not only to Muslim communities but also to global ecological discourse. In an age of existential environmental crisis, this tradition has the potential to reorient our understanding of ethics—from dominion to dependency, from hierarchy to humility, and from exploitation to reverence.

Islamic ecological ethics, then, are not just a contribution to pluralistic environmentalism—they are a paradigm in their own right, offering a path toward restoring harmony with the earth and with the Divine.

CONCLUSION

These findings suggest that Islamic ecological ethics does not simply adjust Western models, but constitutes a distinct framework grounded in the Quran's spiritual cosmology.

The results of this study shed light on an underexplored yet vital contribution of Islamic traditions to global environmental thought. First, these findings suggest that Islamic ecological ethics offers a theocentric alternative to dominant Western paradigms of environmentalism, which often rely on rights-based, utilitarian, or Protestant sentimental models. The Quranic worldview displaces humanity from the centre, positioning all beings as subjects of God's will and praise. This spiritual reorientation carries not only theological implications but also ecological ones, as it challenges exploitative models of nature.

Second, the emphasis on mercy and justice as ethical imperatives reframes sustainability beyond legal or technical definitions. In the Central Asian context, for example, the invocation of divine mercy has become a powerful motivator for environmental action, more resonant than appeals to abstract global targets or economic efficiency. This ethical shift toward eschatology and relational accountability may provide new motivational frameworks for addressing environmental degradation.

Third, this study contributes to the pluralisation of environmental ethics by highlighting non-Western, spiritually grounded epistemologies. While much of the global ecological discourse remains embedded in secular or post-Christian frameworks, Islamic perspectives offer resources for interpreting "the environment" as an ethical construct rather than a neutral backdrop. The Quranic notion of amanah (trust) exemplifies this: it does not imply human superiority but moral responsibility—an interpretive move with far-reaching ecological implications.

Taken together, these findings confirm earlier scholarly insights [e.g., Tlili, 2012; Gade, 2019] while extending them through ethnographic grounding. This study argues that an Islamic environmental ethic is not peripheral or derivative, but instead offers a comprehensive moral framework for life in a time of ecological collapse.

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TOLERANTLIK VA EKOLGIYA MADANIYATI ISLOM AN'ANASIDA

Annotatsiya: Ekologik etika zamonaviy ekologik munozarada tobora muhim omilga aylanib, diniy tadqiqotlar va ekologik gumanitar fanlardan keng qiziqish uyg'otmoqda. Qur'on antroposentrizmga qarshi chiqadigan va tabiiy dunyoga hurmat bilan munosabatda bo'lishga asos soladigan chuqur axloqiy va kosmologik ma'nolarga boy manba sifatida keng tan olingan. Qur'on dunyoqarashining o'ziga xos xususiyati barcha jonzotlarni ruhan ongli va ilohiy ijodda faol ishtirok etuvchi deb tan olishdir. Ushbu teosentrik qarash zamonaviy Markaziy Osiyoda hukmronlik

qilayotgan ierarxik va antroposentrik talqinlarga qarshi chiqadi. So'nggi yigirma yil ichida Sara Tlili va Anna M. Gade kabi olimlar Qur'onni chuqur ekologik tushunchaga olib chiqish uchun katta sa'y-harakatlar qildilar. Ularning yozuvlarida iqlim o'zgarishi va atrof-muhitning yomonlashuvi fonida inson vitse-shohligi (xalifasi) kontseptsiyasini qayta ko'rib chiqish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Biroq, tadqiqotlar tobora ko'payib borayotganiga qaramay, kam sonli tadqiqotlar islom metafizikasi, ayniqsa tavhid (birlik) va amana (ishonch) kabi tushunchalarni ekologik etikada qanday qo'llash mumkinligi masalasiga bag'ishlangan. Ushbu maqola Markaziy Osiyodagi germenevtik tahlil va etnografik ma'lumotlarni birlashtirib, Qur'on qanday qilib ma'naviy integratsiyalashgan ekologiyani ilhomlantirayotganini namoyish etish orqali bu bo'shliqni to'ldirishga harakat qiladi. Tadqiqot adolat va rahm-shafqat atrof-muhitga g'amxo'rlik qilishning axloqiy majburiyatlari sifatida qanday namoyon bo'lishini va insonni Xudoning yaratgani sifatida tushunish inson va tabiat o'rtasidagi yanada barqaror o'zaro aloqaga qanday olib kelishini ko'rsatadi. Shunday qilib, ushbu maqola G'arb dunyoviyligiga asoslangan zamonaviy ekologik munozaraga qarshi chiqadigan va boyitadigan teosentrik paradigmaga hissa qo'shadi. Ekologik etikani tushunish bo'yicha islomiy nuqtai nazar ekologik plyuralizm va inklyuzivlikka asoslanadi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Qur'onning ekologik etikasi, ekologiyasi, teosentrizm, antroposentrizm, amana (ishonch) va tavhid (birlik)

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ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ И ЭКОЛОГИЯ КУЛЬТУРЫ В ИСЛАМСКОЙ ТРАДИЦИИ

Аннотация: Экологическая этика становится все более важным фактором в современном экологическом дискурсе, привлекая широкий интерес со стороны религиоведения и экологических гуманитарных наук. Коран широко известен как источник богатый глубокими этическими и космологическими смыслами, которые бросают вызов антропоцентризму и закладывают основу уважительного отношения к миру природы. Особенной чертой коранического мировоззрения является признание всех существ — как одушевленных, так и неодушевленных — как духовно сознательных и активно участвующих в божественном мире творении. Это теоцентрическое видение бросает вызов иерархическим и антропоцентрическим интерпретациям,

которые доминируют в современной Центрально Азии. В течение последних двух десятилетий такие ученые, как Сарра Тлили и Анна М. Гейд, приложили не мало усилий для выдвижения на первый план глубокого экологического понимания Корана. В их работах подчеркивается необходимость переоценки концепции человеческого наместничества (халифа) в свете изменения климата и деградации окружающей среды. Однако, несмотря на растущий объем исследований, лишь немногие работы рассматривали вопрос о том, как исламская метафизика, особенно такие понятия, как таухид (единство), и амана (доверие) могут быть использованы в экологической этике. В данной статье предпринята попытка восполнить этот пробел, объединив герменевтический анализ и этнографические данные из Центральной Азии, чтобы проиллюстрировать, как Корана вдохновляет на духовно интегрированную в сфере экологии. В исследовании показано, как справедливость и милосердие проявляются в качестве этических императивов для заботы об окружающей среде и как понимание человека как творения божьего приводит к более устойчивому взаимодействию человека с природой. При этом данная статья вносит свой вклад в теоцентрическую парадигму, которая одновременно бросает вызов и обогащает современный экологический дискурс, уходящий корнями в западный секуляризм. Исламская перспектива понимания экологической этики фундирует экологический плюрализм и инклюзивность.

Ключевые слова: экологическая этика Корана, экология, теоцентризм, антропоцентризм, амана (доверие), и таухид (единство)

